

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEED ABILITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656272>

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ABSTRACT: *Undoubtedly, physical education occupies an important place in preschool education.*

KEYWORDS: *Outdoor games, ability, physical exercises, education.*

In no other period of life is physical education so closely related to general education as in the period of preschool childhood. In the first seven years of a child's life, the foundations of health, longevity, and comprehensive motor fitness are laid. Therefore, adults face the important task of strengthening the child's body and the timely development of movements. In order for the process of formation of the child's motor skills to be complete, it is necessary to methodically, consistently build the learning process. The development of motor abilities is one of the most important aspects of the physical education of preschoolers. An increase in mobility, strength and balance in the processes of excitation and inhibition of the central nervous system, as well as the functional maturity of the muscular system, provide a significant increase in the level of development of motor qualities in preschoolers. They are already able to differentiate their muscle efforts, so they can perform exercises with different amplitudes, at a slow and fast pace. This is ensured by an increase in the mobility of nervous processes. A special place in the development of motor abilities is occupied by the development of speed qualities. The high level of their development plays an important role in mastering a number of complex and responsible professions, as well as in achieving high results in various sports.

Scientific research proves that the development of speed qualities in the preschool period creates favorable prerequisites for this. Outdoor games are essential in the development of speed abilities. Compared to any other means of physical education, games are more in line with the needs of a growing organism and contribute to the comprehensive harmonious development of children. Outdoor games in their diversity combine all types of natural movements inherent in a person: walking, running, jumping, wrestling, climbing, throwing, throwing, as well as catching an object, exercises with objects - and that is why they are one of the most versatile and indispensable means of developing speed abilities, the upbringing of whose children is one of the main tasks in physical education classes. Speed abilities are understood as a complex of functional properties of a person, which ensure the performance of motor actions in the minimum period of time for these conditions. There are elementary and complex forms of manifestation of speed abilities. The elementary forms include 4 types of speed abilities: the ability to quickly respond to a signal; the ability to perform single local movements at maximum speed; the ability to

quickly start moving (what is called “sharpness” in practice); the ability to perform movements at a maximum pace. Elementary forms of manifestation of speed abilities in various types of motor activity act in various combinations, forming a complex together with other abilities and skills.

Such complex forms of manifestation include:

1) the ability to quickly pick up speed at the start to the maximum possible (starting speed abilities) - starting acceleration in sprinting, speed skating and rowing;

2) the ability to reach a high level of remote speed (remote speed abilities) - in running, swimming;

3) the ability to quickly switch from one action to another. There are several factors on which the level of development and manifestation of speed abilities depends: the mobility of nervous processes, that is, the speed of transition of nerve centers from a state of excitation to a state of inhibition and vice versa; the ratio of various muscle fibers, their elasticity, extensibility; efficiency of intramuscular and intermuscular coordination; perfection of movement technique; the degree of development of volitional qualities, strength, coordination abilities, flexibility; the content of adenosine triphosphoric acid (ATP) in the muscles, the rate of its breakdown and recovery; ambient temperature. For the development of speed abilities, specific methods are used: the repeated method, the method of a strictly regulated exercise, game, competitive. Also, when developing speed abilities, general didactic methods are widely used: visual, verbal (verbal), practical.

The means of developing speed abilities are exercises performed at or near the maximum speed (the so-called speed exercises). According to Zh.K. Kholodov's means of developing speed abilities can be divided into three main groups: exercises that directly affect individual components of speed abilities, exercises of conjugated influence, exercises of a complex (versatile) impact on all the main components of speed abilities. Physical exercises as a means of physical development are divided into the following types: gymnastics, games, sports exercises and simple tourism. One of the most general classifications is based on historically developed systems of physical education means and methods of their application. Each of these groups has a specific meaning and is divided into even smaller classification subgroups.

Gymnastics in the system of physical education is divided into basic (combat, general developmental exercises, basic movements), sports (acrobatics, rhythmic gymnastics, gymnastics on shells and floor exercises) and auxiliary (sports and auxiliary gymnastics for certain sports, industrial, medical and many others).). Outdoor games are a motor, emotionally colored activity, due to established rules that help to identify the final result or a quantitative result. Sport makes high demands on the physical and spiritual qualities of a person. Therefore, playing sports is permissible only after reaching a certain age and with appropriate physical fitness. In kindergartens, children master only the basics of the technique of sports exercises, which forms the basis for sports in the future. Tourism allows you to consolidate motor skills and develop physical qualities in natural conditions. Performing physical exercises in the fresh air increases their healing effect. In preschool educational institutions, walks are held outside the site and outside the city - the simplest

tourism. In this case, different methods of transportation are used, for example, walking, skiing, cycling. So, outdoor games contribute to the development of speed abilities. Let's consider them in more detail. Outdoor games are based on physical exercises, movements, during which participants overcome a number of obstacles. A mobile game is a type of activity that is characterized by active creative motor actions motivated by its plot. The specificity of the outdoor game is the lightning-fast, instant response of the child to the signal "Catch!", "Run!", "Stop!" and others. In the structure of an outdoor game, content, plot, rules, motor actions are distinguished: the content of an outdoor game is its plot (idea, theme), rules and motor actions. The content comes from the experience of a person, transmitted from generation to generation; the plot of the game determines the purpose of the actions of the participants, the nature of the development of the game conflict. It is borrowed from the surrounding reality and figuratively reflects its actions (for example, hunting, labor, military, household) or is created specifically, based on the tasks of physical education, in the form of a confrontation scheme for various interactions of participants.

The plot of the game not only enlivens the integral actions of the players, but also gives purposefulness to individual techniques and elements of tactics, makes the game exciting; The rules are mandatory requirements for the participants in the game. They determine the location and movement of the players, clarify the nature of the behavior, the rights and obligations of the participants, determine the methods of playing the game, the methods and conditions for accounting for its results. At the same time, the manifestation of creative activity, as well as the initiative of the players within the framework of the rules of the game, are not excluded; motor actions in outdoor games are very diverse. They can be, for example, imitative, figuratively creative, rhythmic; performed in the form of motor tasks that require the manifestation of dexterity, speed, strength and other physical qualities. All motor actions can be performed in various combinations and combinations. Kalinovskaya S.B classifies outdoor games according to several specific criteria: by the number of participants in an outdoor game; by the degree of complexity of the content of the mobile game; by age of children, taking into account age characteristics; by types of movements, mainly included in games; by physical qualities, mainly manifested in the game; depending on the relationship of the players; according to the form of organization; depending on the season and location. According to Stepanenkova E.Ya, outdoor games are classified depending on the level of psychophysical load, taking into account the state of health of children, the degree of activity of the disease process, the physical fitness of children, their psychophysical development, the individual characteristics of the child's personality, indicators of functional tests of the cardiovascular system and other indicators. Psychologists, educators and doctors have long drawn attention to the essential importance of outdoor games for the development of children. Lesgaft P.F. argued that the constant conduct of outdoor games forms in children the ability to control their own movements, and also disciplines his body. Thanks to the game, the child learns to function deftly, deliberately, quickly, as well as follow the rules, appreciate camaraderie and a sense of mutual assistance. Ideas P.F. Lesgaft was successfully promoted by his followers and students V.V. Gorinevsky, E.A. Arkin. E.A. Arkin, a famous school doctor and specialist

in the education of children and adolescents, considered the game a massive means of shaping the child, the “main lever” of education. In his concepts, he said that the game strengthens the child's body, brings joy to his life, and also improves motor abilities. V.V. Gorinevsky considered outdoor play as a way to form a child's personality. He attached great importance to the educational value of the plot of the game and the method of its implementation, as well as the health-improving direction of positive emotions felt by children in the game. He called fun and joy indispensable conditions for playing activity; in the absence of them, the game loses its meaning and meaning, since positive emotions heal the child's body. A.V. Keneman noticed that the formation of speed also takes place in outdoor games with repeated repetitions of actions performed for a long time, as well as in individual sports exercises: for example, skiing, cycling, swings. Their characteristic feature is considered to be activity that is continuously changing both in intensity and in the form of movements, containing the minimum necessary pauses in order to replace the driver, introducing additional barriers. E.N. Vavilova believes that games and physical exercises that develop speed must find a place in numerous forms of physical education.

Running at a moderate pace is used in morning exercises and in the introductory part of a physical education lesson, in separate outdoor games. In the main part of the lesson, running can be with different tasks, in addition, long jumps are included, games with constant motor activity are organized. And in numerous outdoor games that have nothing to do with catching, it is necessary to increase the duration of the run, where a fast pace is not required, but, on the contrary, rhythmic running is encouraged, at a calm, even pace. To develop the speed abilities of preschool children, games are used that develop the ability to quickly pick up speed from the start; games that allow developing the ability to maintain a high level of distance speed; games to develop the ability to quickly switch from one activity to another; games that develop sharpness, games to develop the pace of movement; games that promote the development of the speed of a single movement; games that reduce the time of a simple motor reaction. It is difficult to overestimate the importance of the development of speed abilities of preschool children, as well as the role of outdoor games in this.

Outdoor games are an important means of education, one of the most favorite and useful activities for children. They are based on physical exercises, movements, in the process of which participants overcome a number of obstacles, strive to achieve a certain, pre-set goal due to a wide variety of content and game activities. Outdoor games comprehensively affect the body and personality of the child, contributing to the solution of the most important special tasks of physical education.

Playful activity develops and strengthens the major muscle groups and thus contributes to better health. Outdoor games are the best means of active recreation after hard mental work. Speaking about the importance of outdoor games, it should also be noted that outdoor games are primarily a means of physical education for children. They provide an opportunity to develop and improve their movements, practice running, jumping, climbing, throwing, catching, and so on. After all, a variety of movements require vigorous activity of large and small muscles, contribute to a better metabolism, blood circulation,

respiration, that is, an increase in the vital activity of the body. Outdoor games also have a great influence on the neuropsychic development of the child, the formation of important personality traits that will be characteristic of him throughout his life. They evoke positive emotions, develop inhibitory processes: during the game, children have to react with movement to some signals and refrain from moving with others. In these games, the will, ingenuity, courage, speed of reactions and other useful qualities develop. Joint actions in games bring children together, give them joy from overcoming difficulties and achieving success. The value of outdoor games is that they are one of the most important conditions for the development of a child's culture. In them, he deeply comprehends and cognizes the world around him, his intellect, fantasy, imagination develop in them, social qualities are formed.

Outdoor games are a creative activity in which the child's natural need for movement, the need to find a solution to a motor problem, is manifested. Thus, having considered the concept, characteristics, forms, methods, means of developing the speed abilities of preschoolers, the essence, specifics, structure, classifications, and the significance of outdoor games; it can be concluded that the influence of outdoor games on the development of speed abilities of preschool children is very large.

And adults should not forget that while playing, the child learns and transforms not only himself, but also the world around him.

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